

BoF: The End of RSEng? Challenges and Risks for RSEng

— The future of RSEs —

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Our session pad

Why

- It's only 2025 - we are still working on establishing ourselves.
- We are not yet at the end of RSE!
- We still should think about the challenges ahead, and think about what we can do today.

The setting

- Imagine a world ten years from now \approx 2035
- Kim and Kay, the personas of our position papers are reaching early retirement age.

Some questions

- Which are the topics that we want to have achieved by 2035?
- Definition of RSEs? How will that evolve in ten years? What will not change in the essence of an RSE ten years from now?
- How will RSE change in the face of the ongoing digitalization of society? If people are better prepared in school?
- How will AI impact our work? Is it better than cheap PhDs?
- What will our topics be after VCS don't need to be taught anymore?
- What will change for us with Digitalisation of society? Digitalisation will also feature more heavily in the domain curricula.
- Where has abstraction brought us, and which complexities are now hidden behind it?
- What are new tasks of RTPs?
- What is in this future for RSEs?

A quick refresher

The teachingRSE project

- Formed by an initiative of Heidi Seibold at deRSE23 in Paderborn together with Jan-Philipp Thiele, Jeremy Cohen, Samantha Wittke, and Florian Goth.
- Who of the regulars is here today? Raise your hand!
- Over the following months produced *Foundational Competencies and Responsibilities of a Research Software Engineer*
- This work made it into position paper 002 of de-RSE e.V.

Interested in joining the teachingRSE Project?

- We are a SIG of de-RSE e.V. and also active in the FG RSE of GI.
- Our github organization: <https://github.com/the-teachingRSE-project>
- The github of the learn-and-teach project:
<https://github.com/DE-RSE/learn-and-teach>
- Our ML: <https://www.listserv.dfn.de/sympa/info/jmu-teachingrse>
- Get the details of our weekly meetings

(R)esearch (S)oftware (E)ngineer

People who create or improve research software and/or the structures that the software interacts with in the computational environment of a research domain. They are highly skilled team members who may also choose to conduct their own research as part of their role.

Which Competencies do they need?

Values at the intersection of research and engineering

- Open and fact-based research.
- Transparency, integrity and accountability.
- To take great care to develop software to current best practices.
- Responsible use of digital tools.
- Work towards an inclusive environment for a team.

Rooted in a commitment to integrity, openness, and responsible use of digital tools the RSE uses its technical, research, and team skills to contribute to the success of research projects at all levels of an organisation.

Research Skills

- Skills that enable you to work in a research context *and* participate in it.
- Curiosity(NEW), (Software) Publication(SP), interacting with domain infrastructure(DOMREP), research cycle(RC), ...

Software/Technical Skills

- Skills that enable you to create good software for your community.
- Software lifecycle(SWLC), Software behaviour and analysis(MOD, Program comprehension), creating and distributing software(DOCBB+DIST), ...

Communication Skills

- Skills that facilitate effective interaction with people/teams.
- Teaching(PM), project management(PM), end user or stakeholder interaction(Team+USER), ...

→RSEs are RTPs that bring research skills and software skills to good effect into teams.

From skills to tasks

- Competencies were kept generic on purpose
- What are current day manifestations?

Examples

- Testing (DOCBB,MOD)
- Contributing to larger projects (SWREPOS,SRU,SP,DOCBB,TEAM)
- Mentoring colleagues (SWLC,RC,TEACH)

Dimensions

- Career level
- Project team structures/organisations
- How much digital literacy should be conveyed in standard domain courses?

Specializations

- $\{\text{DOMAIN}\}$ - RSE
- Open Science RSEs
- Project/Community manager RSEs
- Legal-RSEs
- RSE-Teachers
- HPC-RSEs
- ...